

Revitalising the Knowledge Ecosystem: Exploring the Influence of Funding on Acquisition of Information Resources in Academic Libraries in Nigeria.

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Abstract

Purpose/Aims: The study explores the impact of funding on the procurement of information resources in academic libraries in Nigeria.

Methodology: A descriptive research approach was employed. A Google Form was created to gather responses from 35 library staff members across 28 academic libraries in Nigeria. The collected data were analysed and interpreted through frequency counts. The study population includes acquisition librarians from twenty-eight (28) tertiary institution libraries in Nigeria.

Findings: The study found that academic libraries primarily rely on their parent institutions for funding, rather than external donors or alternative sources. Respondents noted that funding shortages have hampered the acquisition and maintenance of both print and electronic resources. The study further emphasises challenges in securing and managing funding, including difficulty persuading individuals and organisations to donate and limited institutional support for fundraising efforts.

Conclusion: The findings show that unpredictable funding has led to inconsistent resource acquisition practices, slowing the growth of comprehensive, up-to-date library collections. These results are significant beyond the library sector because academic libraries' ability to provide access to a wide variety of information resources is vital to the broader knowledge network in higher education.

Study type: Research paper

Keywords: Knowledge Ecosystem, Funding, Information Resources, Library

Introduction

In today's rapidly evolving digital age, academic libraries play a vital role in facilitating knowledge acquisition, research, and intellectual growth within academic communities. However, their effective functioning depends heavily on sufficient funding to acquire and maintain information resources. The knowledge ecosystem is the creation of new knowledge (Carrozza et al., 2020) through interactions among local expertise, innovation, and new markets and economies. Cobben et al. (2022) described a knowledge ecosystem as a way of focusing on how knowledge develops, transfers, interacts, and integrates. In library contexts, a knowledge ecosystem is viewed as a knowledge-based system comprising networks of interconnected people, knowledge, and technological means through which knowledge is created, organised, selected, summarised, and shared with other entities or systems that require it. Given the essential role of university libraries in supporting academic success and knowledge creation, there is increasing recognition of the urgent need to revitalise information dissemination

methods and techniques. Exploring the influence of funding on information acquisition in university libraries offers valuable insights into the challenges these institutions face. It paves the way for informed strategies to improve their functionality. In an era marked by rapid digital transformation, academic libraries are increasingly functioning as knowledge ecosystems—dynamic environments where resources, technologies, scholars, and users interact within a complex, adaptive network. A knowledge ecosystem is not merely a repository of information but a living system that enables the creation, sharing, and evolution of knowledge across institutional and digital boundaries (Saduete & Masalinto, 2023). Within this ecosystem, libraries serve as critical nodes, integrating human expertise, ICT infrastructure, metadata systems, and digital resources to foster innovation and informed decision-making. In Nigeria, academic libraries have undergone significant evolution from traditional collections to digitally enabled environments. Studies indicate that these institutions now play a central role in managing digital holdings, including e-books, e-journals, institutional repositories, and metadata, thereby contributing to the sustainability and growth of knowledge ecosystems.

Insufficient funding poses significant challenges to library services, hindering their ability to meet the evolving needs of students, faculty, and researchers. Several past studies have examined the causes of dwindling library funds, including economic factors, reduced budgetary allocations to libraries, perceptions of libraries among the ruling class, and poor advocacy by library professionals (Akporhonor, 2005; Anyanwu & Akanwa, 2001; Kondylis, 2014). The impact of funding on information acquisition in academic libraries has become a pressing concern. Inadequate financial resources have resulted in limited access to up-to-date books, journals, databases, and other essential scholarly materials (Irenoa, Emilian, & Eru, 2019). This scarcity of resources hampers the ability of both students and faculty members to conduct comprehensive research, ultimately impeding academic progress and stifling innovation. Moreover, the consequences of limited funding extend beyond the immediate constraints on information acquisition. Academic libraries serve as vital hubs for intellectual exchange and collaboration, acting as catalysts for interdisciplinary research and innovation. Insufficient funding not only restricts the acquisition of information resources but also hampers the development of supportive infrastructure, such as modern technologies, study spaces, and expert staff, which are essential for fostering vibrant knowledge ecosystems.

Recent studies highlight the importance of funding for information acquisition in academic libraries. Adequate financial support is crucial for maintaining comprehensive collections that reflect the evolving academic landscape. Funding also directly affects the quality of library services and the ability to meet the diverse information needs of library patrons. Adequate funding is a fundamental requirement for the successful growth of academic libraries. According to Ubogu and Okiy (2011), an academic library must have the resources necessary to achieve its objectives. These resources include well-trained staff and modern information storage and retrieval systems. By examining the interplay between funding availability and information acquisition, this study aims to identify potential solutions, advocate for increased financial support, and ultimately contribute to the revitalisation of knowledge ecosystems in academic libraries.

Statement of problem

Academic libraries are fundamental to the growth and sustainability of a robust knowledge ecosystem, acting as vital centres for information access, knowledge creation, and scholarly communication. In Nigeria, however, their potential is critically impeded by chronic underfunding and unpredictable budget allocations. Despite their indispensable role in enhancing teaching, research, and learning, most Nigerian academic institutions allocate insufficient financial resources to acquire and maintain current and relevant information resources—such as books, journals, electronic databases, and digital repositories. This lack of investment severely hampers libraries' ability to keep pace with technological

innovations and meet rising user expectations in the digital age. Many libraries struggle to update collections, renew journal subscriptions, or invest in essential ICT infrastructure needed for digital access and resource sharing. These challenges are intensified by inflation, foreign exchange fluctuations, and escalating costs of scholarly materials, making resource acquisition increasingly difficult even when funds are available. The scarcity of comprehensive studies linking library funding to the broader knowledge ecosystem overlooks how funding impacts not just collection size, but also access equity, knowledge production, academic innovation, and institutional visibility. This study aims to fill a critical gap by examining how funding patterns directly influence the acquisition of information resources in Nigerian academic libraries and, in turn, how these resources determine the vitality and sustainability of the entire knowledge ecosystem. By analysing both financial inputs and resource acquisition outcomes, this research will offer actionable insights to library administrators, funding agencies, and policymakers—empowering them to make informed decisions that can transform Nigeria’s academic libraries into thriving centres of knowledge and innovation.

Objectives of the study

The specific objectives of this study are to:

- i. Determine the major sources of funds available in academic libraries.
- ii. ascertain the level of funding available in the library;
- iii. highlight the challenges facing funding in academic libraries;
- iv. highlight the frequency of acquisition of information resources in academic libraries;
- v. identify the library resources affected by funding in academic libraries;
- vi. Enumerate the influence of funding on the acquisition of information resources and services in academic libraries.

Review of Related Literature

A library is an essential hub of knowledge and resources, meticulously organised to serve as a vital foundation for reading, research, and security. It is a repository where information—ranging from books and archives to diaries, documents, verified narratives, and data assets—is preserved and made accessible to users and the public. Without a library, educational institutions become fragmented and lack critical information and data, hindering learning and progress. Every educational establishment includes a library, emphasising its crucial role in shaping outcomes and enhancing institutional resilience. Scholastic libraries ignite curiosity and foster learning initiatives within colleges (Ali & Naveed, 2020). By carefully curating both printed and digital collections, libraries enable universities to support academic pursuits effectively, making them indispensable for educational excellence.

The level of funding available to libraries, along with their innovative use of these resources, forms the essential foundation of library services (Irenea et al., 2019). This foundation becomes even more critical during times of limited budget allocations. In recent years, Nigerian academic libraries have experienced a significant decline in financial support and in the availability of diverse sources of funding. As a result, these libraries have struggled to maintain the quality and range of services they once offered, which in turn is affecting their relevance and standing within the academic community. Publicly available data clearly show that the landscape has changed dramatically, and the pivotal role of academic libraries in the tertiary education system has been sharply diminished. The level of funding directly contributes to this shift in public perception. In response, various strategies, such as marketing campaigns, the introduction of new or altered services, and information literacy training programs, have been implemented to attract and retain users. However, these efforts have not yet yielded the desired level of success, highlighting the ongoing challenges academic libraries face in maintaining their significance and effectiveness.

Acquisition of Information Resources in Academic Libraries: Methods and Types

The acquisition function is the first of the three key activities in library technical services, alongside cataloguing and collections management. It also refers to the department responsible for procuring materials for libraries. Abdulsalami and Arowolo (2019) noted that acquisition involves adding items to the library's collections, including purchases, gifts, and exchanges. Quadri and Sodiq (2018) emphasised that acquiring information resources is essential for effective library management in today's information age. Their study found that purchase is the most common method used by academic, public, and special libraries in Kwara State, Nigeria. This aligns with recent research showing that many academic libraries primarily acquire core materials such as textbooks, reference works, and journals in both print and electronic formats through vendors, publishers, and online stores. Books and serial publications remain the primary materials acquired, and due to budget limitations and operational challenges, such acquisitions are often scheduled annually (Zhang & Eschenfelder, 2023; Abdussalam et al., 2021).

Funding in Academic Library

To remain relevant in a constantly evolving, competitive world, this paper examines the current impact of funding on university library services. Perceptions of funding continue to significantly influence the provision of library resources in Nigerian academic libraries, particularly in areas such as information resources, human capital, infrastructure, and service delivery. It is confirmed that university budgets, primarily funded by the government, are the primary source of financial support for these libraries. This reliance on government funding makes libraries vulnerable to budget cuts and policy changes, resulting in insufficient acquisitions and limited development projects (Abdussalam et al., 2021). However, it is now time for academic libraries to explore alternative funding sources to supplement government support. While revenues from overdue fines, photocopying fees, and charges for lost books currently go into the central university account (internally generated revenue), libraries might need to advocate for keeping these funds within their accounts. As Madu et al. (2020) note, money acts as the fuel sustaining all organisations, including libraries. Without adequate funding, librarians struggle to purchase essential facilities and equipment needed to deliver effective services, especially for users with special needs. When funds are lacking, acquiring basic tools like computers, software, and Internet accessories becomes impossible. Financial resources—often provided by a firm or organisation—are necessary to finance specific needs, programs, or projects.

Library funding refers to the process of providing financial resources to build and equip a library. These funds are used for materials, services, and the development of human resources. Funding helps ensure the renewal, maintenance, and longevity of university libraries. Since libraries are part of a larger university system, their budgets are negotiated with the parent organisation, which is responsible for their finances. Typically, their funding comes from the university's budget, covering current expenses. Occasionally, libraries receive support from government ministries like the Ministry of Education, non-governmental organisations, donor agencies, the Tertiary Education Trust Fund, and individuals (Inyang & Igwechi, 2015).

Challenges Facing Funding in Academic Library

Academic libraries are instrumental in generating and sharing knowledge, serving as vital centres for learning, research, and information dissemination. However, they face significant financial challenges that limit their ability to modernise and operate effectively as comprehensive information hubs in today's digital age.

The funding challenges confronting academic libraries, particularly in developing nations like Nigeria, are multi-dimensional and deeply rooted in institutional, economic, and policy frameworks. A foremost

challenge is heavy reliance on government funding. In most public universities, the library budget is a subset of the overall university allocation, which is often inadequate. This single source of funding leaves libraries vulnerable to economic downturns and shifts in government priorities (Abdussalam et al., 2021). Even when libraries receive government support, disbursements are frequently delayed and insufficient. These irregularities hamper long-term planning and disrupt subscription renewals for digital journals and databases, leading to service discontinuities and loss of user confidence (Ajani et al., 2022). Academic libraries contend with rapidly escalating costs of acquiring journals, books, and electronic databases. Currency devaluation in many developing countries further inflates the cost of importing scholarly materials, straining already limited budgets (Zhang & Eschenfelder, 2023). While libraries in advanced economies diversify funding through endowments, grants, and partnerships, many Nigerian libraries lack structured mechanisms for alternative fundraising. There is also limited staff expertise in grant writing and donor engagement. Integrating digital tools such as library management software, institutional repositories, and AI-based systems requires significant financial investment. Many libraries struggle to keep pace with technological advancements due to inadequate funding for infrastructure and training (Farid et al., 2023). Weak national policies on library development and the absence of strong advocacy bodies contribute to persistent underfunding. Library development is often not prioritised in educational policies, and institutional leaders may not fully appreciate the strategic role of libraries in academic excellence. According to a survey conducted by Library Journal, the leading challenge for academic libraries concerns budgets and funding, particularly for acquisitions (Rea, 2021). Adamu, Isah, and Adekunle (2023) found that funding had been a significant problem facing the development of academic libraries in Africa. Nonetheless, the study discovered that some issues affecting the funding of university libraries include under-qualified librarians, a negative public perception of librarians, and inadequate infrastructure.

Methodology

The descriptive research method was used for this study. The data collection instrument was a Google Form. The collected data were analysed and interpreted. The study population comprised 35 acquisition librarians across twenty-eight (28) tertiary institution libraries in Nigeria. To ensure the credibility of the data collection tool, the questionnaire used in this study underwent both face and content validation. The instrument was reviewed by three experts in Library and Information Science and Educational Measurement and Evaluation, who assessed the relevance, clarity, and coverage of each item. Based on their feedback, necessary modifications were made to enhance the instrument's validity. A pilot study was then conducted using 10 acquisition librarians from institutions not included in the main study population. The responses were analysed using Cronbach's Alpha to determine the internal consistency of the instrument. The reliability coefficient obtained was 0.87, indicating a high level of reliability.

Data Analysis and Interpretation

Table 1: Distribution of Participating Institutions and Staff Responses

S/N	Name of Institution	No. of Responses
1	Osun State University	1
2	Redeemer's University	1
3	Ekiti State Polytechnic	1

4	Afe Babalola University, Ado-Ekiti	1
5	University of Ibadan	1
6	Adeleke University	2
7	Ladoke Akintola University of Technology, Ogbomosho	1
8	Bowen University	1
9	OAU, Ile-Ife	1
10	Federal Polytechnic Offa (Kwara)	4
11	University of Lagos	1
12	Federal University of Technology, Minna	1
13	Kaduna Polytechnic	1
14	Ojaja University, Kwara State	1
15	Kwara State University (Malete)	2
16	University of Nigeria, Nsukka	1
17	Fountain University, Osogbo	2
18	University of Port Harcourt	1
19	Akanu Ibiam Federal Polytechnic, Unwana, Ebonyi State	1
20	Michael Okpara University of Agriculture, Umudike	1
21	DUFUHS, Uburu	1
22	Lower Niger River Basin Development Authority	1
23	Donald Ekong Library, Univ. of Port Harcourt, Rivers State	1
24	Federal Polytechnic, Ede	1
25	Federal College of Education, Iwo	2
26	Adeseun Ogundoyin Polytechnic, Eruwa	1
27	Osun State University, Okuku Campus	1
28	Lens Polytechnic, Offa	1

A total of 35 valid responses were received from library staff across 28 tertiary institutions. Some institutions, such as Adeleke University, Federal Polytechnic Offa, Kwara State University, Fountain University, and FCE Iwo, contributed multiple responses mainly because they have more than one

acquisition librarian. This reflects the collaborative nature of acquisition work and the division of responsibilities among several professionals in larger or more complex library systems. Including responses from a diverse range of universities, polytechnics, and colleges of education offers a comprehensive view of acquisition practices and funding issues within Nigerian tertiary education. The varied participation improves the study's reliability and ensures the findings represent different institutional types and operational capacities.

What are the major sources of fund in your library

35 responses

The analysis of funding sources across 35 libraries reveals that the parent institution is the dominant source, accounting for a substantial 80% of library funding. This heavy reliance on institutional budgets reflects the traditional funding model prevalent in many academic libraries, particularly in developing countries like Nigeria. Other sources of funding, such as donor agencies, internally generated revenue (IGR), wealthy individuals, and miscellaneous sources, make up the remaining 20%, each contributing a small fraction. The low percentage of external or diversified funding underscores a critical vulnerability: libraries are significantly affected by fluctuations or limitations in their parent institution's financial allocations. This finding highlights the urgent need for academic libraries to diversify their funding base by developing strategic partnerships, seeking grants, and enhancing their internal revenue generation capacity to ensure sustainability and improved service delivery.

How will you describe the level of funding in your library

35 responses

The data shows that 57.1% of respondents believe the library suffers from inadequate funding. This majority view reflects a significant concern about financial support for library services. One possible explanation is the strong representation of public institutions in the sample. These institutions often face

budget constraints and bureaucratic delays that limit consistent investment in library resources. This finding highlights a recurring challenge in the public education sector: the struggle to prioritise library funding amid competing institutional needs. It suggests the need for policy reforms or dedicated library grants to ensure equitable access to quality information resources.

What are the challenges of Fundraising and Advocacy experienced in your library

35 responses

The chart shows that 34.3% of respondents identified difficulty convincing individuals and organisations, along with a lack of institutional support, as the main challenges in library fundraising. This reflects a broader issue: libraries often struggle to communicate their value to potential donors and may lack internal backing to drive fundraising efforts. In contrast, 17% cited receiving irrelevant or unneeded resources from donor agencies. This indicates a mismatch between what is offered and what is actually useful, suggesting poor communication or a lack of needs-based planning in donor relationships. Overall, the responses reveal that core fundraising issues stem more from structural and strategic weaknesses than from a total absence of donor interest. Addressing these challenges will likely require stronger advocacy, clearer fundraising strategies, and more targeted engagement with donors.

What is the frequency of acquisition of information resources in your library?

35 responses

The chart shows that a large majority, 71.4%, of respondents say the frequency with which they acquire information resources in their library is not clearly defined. This suggests a lack of structured planning or consistent funding cycles, which could lead to irregular updates and resource gaps. Conversely, 25.7% reported that acquisitions happen annually, indicating only a small number of libraries follow a set, predictable schedule for updates. This highlights a systemic issue: most libraries lack a formal acquisition strategy, probably due to uncertain or inconsistent funding. Without a clear schedule,

libraries may find it challenging to meet users' changing information needs or keep their collections current.

What resources are mostly affected by inadequate funding

35 responses

The chart shows that print resources are most impacted by inadequate funding, with 57.1% of respondents indicating this. Online databases and electronic resources follow, at 20% and 17.1%, respectively. Despite the growing trend toward digital access, print materials remain a key part of library collections, especially where digital infrastructure is limited. The significant effect on print resources may be due to rising acquisition and maintenance costs or lower funding prioritisation. The lower percentages for online databases and electronic resources could suggest less dependence or support, such as consortium access or donor funding that offsets expenses. Overall, the impact across all resource types underscores the broader challenges facing library budgets and emphasises the need for a balanced funding approach that supports both print and digital resources.

What other ways do you think dwindling fund allocation affected your library

35 responses

The findings show that 51.4% of respondents believe that decreased funding has affected their libraries by limiting access to ongoing professional development, such as conference sponsorships. This indicates that budget reductions not only impact resources but also hinder the growth and capacity of library staff. Moreover, 34.3% noted that the inability to attract or retain qualified professionals is another significant consequence of insufficient funding. This reveals a deeper systemic problem: when libraries lack funds, they struggle not just with building collections but also with maintaining a skilled workforce essential for delivering quality services. Overall, these responses highlight how financial

shortages weaken both the human and professional bases of libraries, diminishing their capacity to adapt, innovate, and serve users effectively.

Discussion of findings

The study highlights a persistent funding shortfall in Nigerian academic libraries, critically limiting their ability to meet the increasing and diverse needs of users. This aligns with Adamu, Isah, and Adekunle (2023), who noted that insufficient funding is a primary obstacle to the development of academic libraries across the continent. Financial constraints often lead to inadequate infrastructure, staffing, and resources, which diminish service quality and research support. Fundraising challenges further expose systemic gaps in resource mobilisation, with many respondents citing a lack of strategic backing and weak outreach efforts to potential donors. Dissatisfaction with donor-provided resources also indicates a mismatch between library needs and donor priorities, likely due to communication issues or an underdeveloped advocacy culture. These results support earlier research identifying poor advocacy, a negative librarian image, and low institutional investment as key factors in chronic underfunding (Adamu et al., 2023). An additional concern is the irregular acquisition of information resources, hindered by the lack of structured policies, which reduces the ability to maintain comprehensive, up-to-date collections. Irenoa, Emilian, and Eru (2019) also reported that limited and inconsistent funding severely hampers the procurement of current publications and digital databases. The impact of funding shortages varies across resource types, with print materials—still vital—most affected, followed by electronic resources and online databases. This trend suggests a disproportionate neglect of traditional resources amid a shift to digital, possibly due to budget reallocations or cost considerations. Failing to balance investments in physical and digital collections may limit libraries' ability to adapt to changing academic demands.

Conclusion

This study critically assessed how funding impacts the acquisition of information resources in Nigerian academic libraries, emphasising its vital role in maintaining a dynamic knowledge system. These libraries are key hubs in this system, enabling knowledge flow, preservation, and creation vital for scholarly progress and national growth. However, ongoing underfunding has seriously hindered this ecosystem, limiting libraries' capacity to access current resources, sustain acquisition activities, and meet the evolving needs of students, researchers, and faculty. Reviving Nigeria's academic knowledge system requires more than just increased funding; it calls for a strategic overhaul of libraries, which are essential infrastructure for innovation, research, and capacity enhancement. This involves advocating for sustainable funding methods, fostering collaborative partnerships, improving librarians' professional standing, and integrating libraries more deeply into institutional and national research bodies. Strengthening these knowledge networks is crucial for enabling academic libraries to realise their transformative potential in the digital era.

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